

**William Sutherland,
Professor of Conservation
Biology and Director of
Research, University of
Cambridge**

Open access means equitable access to research

– William Sutherland

Publishing books open access enables academics and conservationists across the world to access and act on important research and evidence

Books have always been very important to William Sutherland. Research and evidence are vital to his work as a conservationist and vital to others in his field. So the Professor of Conservation Biology and Director of Research in the Department of Zoology at the University of Cambridge, was shocked to discover how many academics and community groups across the world were denied access to much of the academic research.

Research that is priced out of reach

When researching his book *The Conservation Handbook*, Sutherland travelled the world, visiting the libraries in the countries he visited. That was when he realised how difficult it was for local conservationists to access research – libraries were often locked or poorly stocked as they could not afford to buy expensive academic books or pay hefty subscription fees. Sutherland said:

“ Books are only accessible to a limited number of people and where there’s the greatest need for conservation, these books are hardest to acquire and hardest to afford.

Giving books away for free

Sutherland wanted to get his research into the hands of people he thought needed it most, so he struck a deal with his publisher – he would forego his royalties, spending the money on distributing free copies of his book. For every book sold, another was sent to a practitioner, free of charge, giving them access to knowledge. A total of 3362 free copies were shared this way.

He said:

“I wanted to make a difference. I want to have an impact on the world and I want the world to be a better place.”

Sutherland did the same with a series of books he edited and set up a website called Conservation Evidence, where he and a team of like-minded academics compile an open access database of the scientific literature.

Academics are paid to be researchers

While acknowledging that some people need royalties from their books, Sutherland thinks research should be accessible to as many people as possible across the globe, not just those in the Global North. He says publishing open access goes a long way to achieving that, and that his work has had much greater reach and impact by making it freely available.

He added:

“If you’re an academic, you’re paid to work. Rather than concentrating on making a small amount of money out of writing a book, why not concentrate on getting it read and making a difference? Because that’s our job.”

Equitable models of publishing

Sutherland has published nine books open access and in 2023, the Conservation Evidence project won the Vice-Chancellor’s 2023 Award for Research Impact and Engagement for the most impactful research at Cambridge University. He is a firm

believer in open access, but says there are challenges that need to be addressed so that everybody can afford to publish, not just those with deep pockets or wealthy universities to fund them.

“ We need to ensure we do not move from a world where only an elite can read the scientific books and journals to a world in which only an elite can publish books and papers due to publishing fees. That is a concern, and we need to make sure we have the solutions.